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DESIGN FOR RIVER SIGN
A CASE STUDY OF MIKUMAGAWA RIVER

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ABSTRACT

This project decided upon rules for designing river signs and also designed a case-study. In Japan, a great variety of signs are used at rivers and their surroundings. The information on these signs is diverse. Signs include such information as the name of the river; prohibitions, rules and recommended behavior at the river and its surroundings; and introductions to the history and culture of the river and its locality. The signs are haphazardly placed, and lack rules about the presentation of information. In our opinion, this is a primary cause of people's difficulty with comprehending the signs, and causes harm to the river landscape. Therefore, this project concerns the design of signs that will be easily understood by the people and prevent damage to the river landscape.

Keywords: Sign, River, Pictogram

INTRODUCTION

River spaces provide a place to enjoy walks and sports, water play, events and suchlike in our lives but, as natural spaces, they can also pose a danger to our lives at times such as flooding due to heavy rain. Accordingly, there are many rules concerning points we need to be careful of when using river spaces, and manners to make it more pleasant for everyone to use these spaces. The sight of illustrated board signs placed here and there in the river area announcing warnings and behavior recommendations and river name signs installed like road signs by the river are a familiar one at rivers all over Japan. In recent years, as river spaces have come to be environmentally planned as local community water areas, the lag in coordination of river sign designs

has become noticeable, and improvements are needed urgently.

The aims of this project were to provide river signs that fulfilled the function of providing information to users of river spaces while enhancing the landscape, through the design of signs that were appealing, had visual impact and were consistent, to draw up design rules related to river signs, and to publish guidelines summarizing the above. A further aim was to create a model area of river signs based on these guidelines around the Mikuma river (the upriver district of the Chikugo river) flowing from Hita city in Oita prefecture, and to improve awareness regarding river signs among those responsible for placing the signs, the river administrators (hereafter referred to as administrators).

SURVEY OF THE PRESENT STATE OF RIVER SIGNS

OVERVIEW OF SURVEY OF PRESENT STATE

In order to understand the present state of river signs, a field study was conducted. The survey was conducted by walking with administrators along various stretches of the Chikugo river (Kyushu region), namely, Hita city in Oita prefecture, Kurume city in Fukuoka prefecture and Ukiha city in Fukuoka prefecture, interviewing them as the survey was conducted. Points of observation in the study were type of sign, place of setting, method of setting, content, and intention in putting up the sign. Based on this study, river signs were categorized as in Table 1.

Table 1. Classification of river signs

Category	Type	Sub-type	Content and aim
Rules	Prohibitions	No entry	Notification that it is prohibited to enter a certain river area or facility
		Restrictions in use	Restrictions in user behavior, notification that bringing cars into the river area or parking is prohibited etc.
		Prevention	Notification about prohibition of illegal dumping of waste etc.
	Warnings	Warnings intended to prevent accidents such as those caused by rising waters or falls	
Education	Behavior recommendations		Notification of manners regarding use, such as restrictions on disposal of garbage and dealing with pet waste
Names	Name of facility		Notification of role and function of pump towers, floodgates etc.
	Name of river		Notification of the name of the river etc.
Guidance/ explanation	Guide to facility		Notification of the role and function of river facilities such as pump towers and water gates, notification of role of user centers etc. managed by the river office
	History/nature		Notification of history of floods, introduction to historical ruins and information about the surrounding natural environment etc.

SUMMARY OF SURVEY OF PRESENT STATE

Many of the signs set in river spaces are there to give prohibitions or warnings, or to provide behaviour recommendations, but the fact that there is no system to the creation and setting of these signs at present is a major issue (Figure 1). The main issues surrounding river signs are outlined below.

- Information of varying importance is expressed using similar illustrations, making it difficult for users to realize the differences in levels of importance.
- There are no rules regarding graphic expression, so the same information is expressed in different ways, which does not encourage effective learning among users.
- Signs are not valued by the community because they were not made with consideration for the surrounding environment and local features.

Figure 1. Standard river signs in Japan

CONCEPT OF DESIGN RULES FOR RIVER SIGNS

In terms of strategies to resolve the issues that arose from the survey of the present state, the following design rules (Figure 2) were established and applied in relation to the most frequently occurring river signs, which tend to concern prohibition, warnings, or behaviour recommendations.

- Pictograms will be used to transmit information in an easily understandable way.

Pictograms rather than illustrations will be used on signs because information from illustrations can vary according to different tastes, and avoiding this confusion by using the same pictogram for the same information at all river sites can lead to common understanding among users and higher learning effectiveness.

- Rules will be established for using colors corresponding to the importance of the information.

Prohibitions and behavior recommendations differ in their importance. In order to make this clear at first glance, signs with prohibitions should use red, warnings should use yellow, and behavior recommendations should use green.

- Information will be laid out in a concise and easily comprehensible manner.

The text should be written with headings and simple sentences. Specialized language will not be used, so that the language is understandable even to a child. In addition, to allow for multiple signs to be placed at one site, signs will be configured with two squares. The top square will have a pictogram and the bottom square will have the text.

It is necessary for prohibition signs, unlike warnings and behaviour recommendations, to transmit the prohibited action clearly to users, due to the risk of major accidents if they are not properly employed. As such, as shown in Figure 3 patterns and 4 versions of prohibitions were examined. The first pattern was a restrictive expression using a simplified version of the 'NO' used on traffic signs and so on. This was the most generalized sign and the one easiest for users to understand. However, as the restrictive expression took up a large part of the limited space on the sign, it became more difficult to understand the pictogram explaining the prohibited action, meaning

The importance of the information.	High	Middle	Low
	Prohibition	Warning	Recommendation behaviour
Sign's Color	Red	Yellow	Green

Example	High (Red)	Middle (Yellow)	Low (Green)

Figure 2. New design rules of river signs

that it was easy to understand that a restriction was in force, but difficult to understand what was being restricted. The second pattern was a restrictive expression using the X symbol. Two versions of this pattern were examined, one using thinner lines and one using thicker lines. However, while Japanese people recognize the X symbol as a negative, alternative interpretations of X meaning 'unknown' or X meaning 'target' are also possible. Moreover, if several prohibition signs were set up alongside each other, there would be a line of X symbols, and this would emphasize the impression of use restrictions, which would not be ideal for a river space serving a function as a place of recreation and relaxation. The third pattern was a restrictive expression using a diagonal line. Prohibition was expressed by drawing a diagonal line through the pictogram. The proportion of the sign taken up by the restrictive expression was not too great, the pictogram expression was still clear, the visual impression was not too overbearing even when signs were set in a row, and so a decision was made to employ the restrictive expression using a diagonal line.

Furthermore, the guidelines included details on the base colors and recommended colors for red, yellow and green respectively, leaving the possibility to select color tones to fit with the environment in which signs were placed. As a number of river signs are often set in a row, it is easy to give the impression of the signs being crowded. To prevent this, signs were configured as a unit consisting of 2 squares, one above the other, making it easier for those setting up the signs to set them in a line, while

Figure 3. Method of showing prohibition

Figure 4. A part of the signs made

users could be given an impression of systematic orderliness.

In order to create signs that will be valued by the community, it is also noted in the guidelines that a place for discussion with local residents about the establishment of signs should be created, and a process of decision-making should be adopted that involves discussion about materials and size of signs appropriate to the locality and specific place they will be located. Figure 4 shows a part of the signs made according to the above-mentioned rule.

Figure 5. Signs set up in Mikuma river

CREATION OF A MODEL AREA FOR RIVER SIGNS

The first area selected as a model area for river signs was the Mikuma river area, flowing from Hita city in Oita prefecture. Although it is generally known as the Mikuma river, its official name is the Chikugo river, and it is the upriver area of the Chikugo river. It has been known as the Mikuma river by local residents from times past. The area selected for establishing signs was the area around the 6km walkway around the riverbed completed in March 2009, the Hita hot spring area and the parks and areas used for recreation and relaxation by local residents.

In December 2008, a 'Committee to Investigate Suikyou Hita River Signs' was established within the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism Kyushu Regional Bureau Chikugo River River Office, and a total of 8 meetings were held in the period up to March 2010. Members of the committee were employees of Hita city, the head of the Hita Tourist Association, a representative of the Hita Hot Spring Ryokan Union Proprietresses' Group, heads of the relevant residents' associations and women's groups, representatives of groups engaged in NPO activities with a focus on the Mikuma river, the dam manager of the Mikuma upriver dam, university professors and others. At each meeting, there was agreement, examination and discussion about the

river signs and related matters. At the first meeting, it was explained to committee members that design rules for river signs were being drawn up, and members' understanding regarding the coordination of signs in line with these design rules was obtained.

The river signs examined in this project were name signs, guidance and explanation signs and distance signs (Figure 5). Traditionally, most river name signs have taken the same form as road signs, being written horizontally, but there is a high chance that horizontal signs could obstruct people's view, spoiling their enjoyment of river scenery from the river bank, and so a plan for vertical signs in addition to horizontal signs was proposed as a way of taking this view into consideration.

It was decided through discussion that the guidance and explanation signs, which would be placed along the walking route, would contain information about sights and maps of the walking route. However, as there were some places where only a map was necessary and other places where both a map and an explanation were necessary, a unit-style guidance and explanation sign formed of a base and surface (Figure 5, center top and bottom) was proposed with a view to making sure that such differences did not have a major impact on the production process and costs. Furthermore, through integration of prohibition signs too, guidance and explanation signs and prohibition signs could be

combined freely according to the specific circumstances of the location, facilitating further prevention of the impression of crowdedness of signs. It was also made possible to set up the base only (Figure 5, bottom right) for now with a view to locating prohibition signs at the spot at some point in the future.

As far as the distance signs were concerned, it was not deemed necessary to emphasize their existence strongly, and they were designed in such a way that people who wanted to use them would notice them, but they would otherwise blend easily into the environment of the river bank. All of the signs were made using locally produced Hita stone, and all the design plans were explained, discussed and agreed on at committee meetings.

SUMMARY AND FUTURE

The major achievement of implementing this project was being able to change the awareness among administrators responsible for setting up signs. While administrators had their doubts about whether signs were fulfilling their intended function, they had got into the habit of setting up signs as a way of dealing with each incident, and had not achieved any drastic reform. However, by examining various issues together with administrators in this project, and by drawing up basic rules and publishing guidelines, we were able to make administrators realise the importance of continued collaboration with community residents in maintaining management after signs had been established, and the necessity of providing signs that were easily comprehensible to users while taking the environment into consideration. Moreover, by creating a model area for river signs and organizing it in line with the guidelines, it was possible to show clearly how a river scene different from previous river scenes could be arranged.

In the future, it is hoped that the concrete example of the Mikuma river will gradually spread to be implemented in a similar way at other rivers. There are many signs apart from river name signs and prohibitions that need to be improved around rivers. It would be worthwhile to examine these issues in the same way, adopting a bottom-up approach to river signs in general. Finally, we would like to take this opportunity to express our gratitude

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※Design rights have been obtained for the prohibition, warning and behavior recommendation signs developed in this project (shown in Figure 4).
 ※The resulting products of this project received the 2010 Good Design Award (Social field: Town and community development).

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